

COMPETENCY ASSESSMENT OF BATANGAS MARINE PROTECTED AREA AND BANTAY DAGAT NETWORKS: BASIS FOR CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Competency of people determines the fate of organizations in any endeavor. This study assesses the levels of competencies of people involved in a conservation strategy in the form of a marine protected area (MPA) and a bantay dagat (BD) networks in the Province of Batangas. The purpose is to formulate a capacity development program that is tailor-fitted to needs assuring the success of this strategy. The study conducted survey, key informant interviews (KII) and focus group discussion (FGD) with seventy-nine (79) respondents, sixteen (16) are senior managers, thirteen (13) are skilled workers, forty (40) are MPA stakeholders and 10 are technical specialist. The following conclusions were drawn from findings of the study: (1) Level of competencies of all MPA managers and Bantay Dagat in planning and communication are high while the level of competencies of some MPA managers and Bantay Dagat are low to moderate in financing, enforcement and monitoring and evaluation. (2) Stakeholders were satisfied in the competencies of MPA managers and Bantay Dagat in terms of planning and communication and moderately satisfied in terms of financing, enforcement and monitoring and evaluation (M&E). (3) Difference on the level of competencies of MPA manager and Bantay Dagat in knowledge in enforcement and M&E was significant when grouped according to their age. (4) Problems, issues and challenges fall under: Fiscal Administration, Human Resources Management/Human Resource Development, Organizational Structure, Public Policy and Program Administration, Technology Management, Voluntary Sector Management/People Involvement, and Environmental Management.

Keywords: competency, conservation strategy, marine protected area, Bantay Dagat, Province of Batangas